

SELECTING METHODS OF SIGNIFICANT DATA FROM GATHERED DATASETS FOR RESEARCH

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Annotation. Nowadays, the development of artificial intelligence, the emergence of optimal decision-making opportunities with the help of machine learning algorithms is increasing interest in data analysis. Because making optimal decisions with the help of intelligent algorithms is closely related to the analysis of primary data. One of the most important steps in data analysis is extracting the necessary data from the collected dataset. In this research work, opinions are given about the methods of extracting important data for achieving the intended objective function from the data set formed. The results of the practical experience obtained during the research are described.

Keywords. Data analysis; correlation coefficient; Pearson, Spearman, and Kendall correlation coefficients; dataset for the optimization problem of internal distribution.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that today data analysis is one of the most widely used areas of research in all fields. The main goal of this direction is to help make optimal decisions by identifying the hidden contents and patterns in the data set [1,2]. These decisions can be decisions to predict the future based on available datasets or to determine the main strategies in management processes, such as classifying or clustering objects. Of course, the accuracy of these decisions is closely related to the collected data [3-6]. Therefore, in order to achieve the objective function in

the developed model, the correct formation of the data set is a very important step.

Usually, when studying the factors affecting the work of a system, as much information as possible is collected about the environment that is part of this system and surrounds it [7,8]. Of course, this helps to gain more insight into the system's performance, but some information may not be relevant to achieving the target function in the model being developed. Even in some cases, some information contained in the formed data set may give a wrong direction in achieving the objective function. Therefore, determining the dependence of the information contained in the collected data set on the developed model is a relevant part of the research conducted in systematic analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The most widely used approach to solving the above problem is the use of methods for determining the correlation coefficient of these variables. There are several methods for determining the correlation coefficient of data in a data set, and it is important to determine which one should be chosen for the data collected in the study. In this process, it is necessary to pay attention to the following characteristics of the data set [9]:

- ✓ Linear or non-linear relationship between data (variables);
- ✓ To the normal distribution of the data in the data set;
- ✓ Measurements of data values;
- ✓ Existence of data limitations.

The method of determining the required correlation coefficient is chosen according to which of the above-mentioned features are embodied in the aggregated data set. Pearson, Spearman, and Kendall's methods are the most commonly used correlation methods in research.

According to the Pearson method, the correlation coefficient of two data sets u and v is found by the following formula (1):

$$r_{uv} = \frac{k \cdot \sum uv - \sum u \cdot \sum v}{\sqrt{[k \cdot \sum u^2 - (\sum u)^2] \cdot [k \cdot \sum v^2 - (\sum v)^2]}} \quad (1)$$

where r_{uv} - correlation coefficient of u and v , k – number of values, $\sum u$ - sum of u values list, $\sum v$ - sum of v values list, $\sum uv$ - sum of the product of u and v values, $\sum u^2$ - sum of squares of u values, $\sum v^2$ - sum of squares of v values.

Pearson's formula for determining the correlation coefficient is generally used when the distribution of data is expected to be linear, the data set has a normal distribution, and there are no restrictions imposed on the data.

According to the Spearman method, the correlation coefficient of two variables u and v is found by the following formula (2):

$$r_{uv} = 1 - \frac{6 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k z_i^2}{k(k^2 - 1)} \quad (2)$$

where z_i is the difference of variables of the appropriate order in the set u and v , i.e. $z_i = u_i - v_i$. Spearman's formula is usually used when the distribution between the data is non-linear and has a random distribution.

The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the linear relationship between variables in a data set. The Spearman correlation coefficient represents the proportional monotonic change of variables.

Using Kendall's formula, the correlation coefficient of two variables is also used, as in Spearman's formula, when the gap between the data is not linear and has an arbitrary distribution. According to Kendall's method, the correlation coefficient of two variables u and v is found by the following formula (3):

$$r = \frac{F - E}{k \cdot (k - 1)} \quad (3)$$

where F is the number of pairs satisfying condition (4) for $(u_i : v_i)$ and $(u_i : v_i)$,

and $E = k - F$.

$$\left[(u_i < u_j) \text{ and } (v_i < v_j) \right] \text{ or } \left[(u_i > u_j) \text{ and } (v_i > v_j) \right] \quad (4)$$

where $i < j$ and $i, j = 1..k$.

In all three methods, the value of the correlation coefficient is found in the range [-1:1]. Here, -1 means perfect inverse proportionality, 1 means perfect direct proportionality, and 0 means no correlation between the variables at all. In general, the value of the correlation coefficient can be interpreted as shown in Table 1 below [11]:

Table 1. Interpretation of the value of the correlation coefficient

The value of the correlation coefficient	Explanation of the value of the correlation coefficient
-1.00 : -0.90	Inversely proportional quantities with a very strong correlations
-0.89 : -0.70	Inversely proportional quantities with good correlation
-0.69 : -0.40	Inversely proportional quantities with average correlations
-0.39 : -0.10	Inversely proportional quantities with a weak correlations
-0.10 : -0.00	Inversely proportional quantities with negligible correlations
0.00 : 0.10	Properly proportional quantities with negligible correlations
0.10 : 0.39	Properly proportional quantities with weak correlations
0.40 : 0.69	Properly proportional quantities with moderate correlations
0.70 : 0.89	Properly proportional quantities with good correlation
0.90 : 1.00	Properly proportional quantities with very strong

	correlations
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It should be noted that the correlation coefficient shows that the data studied in this study are statistically related to each other. The fact that the correlation coefficient is statistically significant does not always mean that it is practically significant. And on the contrary, a small correlation coefficient does not always mean that it is practically insignificant. But it should be kept in mind that in a large data set, a small correlation coefficient can draw attention to statistics and give confusing opinions in some cases [11-12].

RESULTS.

The above-mentioned 3 correlation coefficient determination methods were used in the study of the factors affecting the query time in internal distributed computing systems. In these experiments, a data set consisting of 500 tuples containing the following information was formed: 1) d_t is the total number of tuples in the database; 2) t_n is the number of distributed tables in the database; 3) s is the time (seconds) required to process requests in distributed tables in the database; 4) v - the total volume of information in the database; 5) d_r_v - the speed of reading data from the hard disk (Mbytes/second); 6) ram_v – RAM size (Mbytes); 7) ram_w – operating memory frequency (MHz); 8) t_v - speed of data transfer of RAM (Mbyte/second); 9) cpu_w – processor frequency (MHz); 10) cpu_n – number of processor cores; 11) L1 – 1- cache memory size (Mbyte); 12) L2 – 2nd cache memory size (Mbyte); 13) L3 – 3rd cache memory size (Mbytes);

According to the results of the experiment, the Spearman method was the most reliable of the above 3 methods. This result can be seen in Figure 1 below.

s	1.00	0.66	-0.61	0.57	-0.29	-0.31	-0.27	-0.27	-0.33	-0.27	-0.27	-0.27	-0.27
d_t	0.66	1.00	0.01	0.98	-0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
t_n	-0.61	0.01	1.00	0.14	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
v	0.57	0.98	0.14	1.00	-0.01	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
d_r_v	-0.29	-0.00	0.01	-0.01	1.00	0.70	0.44	0.44	0.80	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.54
ram_v	-0.31	0.00	0.01	-0.00	0.70	1.00	0.92	0.92	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96
ram_w	-0.27	0.00	0.01	-0.00	0.44	0.92	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89
t_v	-0.27	0.00	0.01	-0.00	0.44	0.92	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89
cpu_w	-0.33	-0.00	0.01	-0.00	0.80	0.96	0.89	0.89	1.00	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83
cpu_n	-0.27	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.96	0.89	0.89	0.83	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
L1	-0.27	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.96	0.89	0.89	0.83	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
L2	-0.27	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.96	0.89	0.89	0.83	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
L3	-0.27	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.96	0.89	0.89	0.83	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	s	d_t	t_n	v	d_r_v	ram_v	ram_w	t_v	cpu_w	cpu_n	L1	L2	L3

Figure 1. Correlation coefficients determined using the Spearman method

CONCLUSION

In short, data analysis is a very important stage in the research process of data sorting to achieve the objective function for the developed model. Three Pearson, Spearman and Kendall methods were considered to solve the problem posed in this article. From the results of the experiment, it was found that among these three methods, the formula for finding the correlation coefficient of Spearman was found to be the most effective for the problem set in the research.

REFERENCES

1. Komolov S. & Raxmatov Sh. “Sun’iy intellekt asoslari. Mashinaviy o’qitish” Innopolis University, Ijod nashr, 2022, 117 p
2. Akhatov A. & Rashidov A. “Big Data va unig turli sohalaridagi tadbiqi”, Descendants of Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi, 2021, № 4 (18), 135-44
3. Joaquin Vanschoren “Real-world machine learning pipelines. Data preprocessing” 2019, 67 p

4. Akhatov A., Renavikar A., Rashidov A. & Nazarov F. “*Development of the Big Data processing architecture based on distributed computing systems*” Informatika va energetika muammolari O‘zbekiston jurnali, № (1) 2022, 71-79
5. Alan Lee “*Data Preprocessing, Imputation and Feature Engineering*” STATS 2017, 40 p
6. Rashidov A.E. “*Pre-processing algorithms in intellectual analysis of Data Flow*” “Science and education in the modern world: challenges of the XXI century” XII International scientific and practical conference, Astana, Kazakhstan, February 2023, 52-54 p
7. Rashidov A., Akhatov A., Nazarov “*Real-Time Big Data Processing Based on a Distributed Computing Mechanism in a Single Server*” Stochastic Processes and Their Applications in Artificial Intelligence, 121-138 DOI: 10.4018/978-1-6684-7679-6
8. Akhatov A., Renavikar A., Rashidov A. “*Optimization of the database structure based on Machine Learning algorithms in case of increased data flow*” Proceedings of the International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Computing And Security (ICABCS 2023), Gr. N01 Da, Up, India, 24-25 February 2023
9. Bhandari, P. “*Correlation Coefficient | Types, Formulas & Examples*” 2022, December 05, from <https://www.scribbr.com/statistics/correlation-coefficient/>
10. Rashidov A. “*Real vaqtda katta hajmdagi ma’lumotlarni yagona serverda qayta ishlash arxitekturasi*” Fan, ta’lim va ishlab chiqarishni rivojlanishida yosh olimlarning o‘rni, 2022.09.30, 74-76
11. Patrick Schober, Christa Boer, Lothar A. Schwarte “*Correlation Coefficients: Appropriate Use and Interpretation*” Anesthesia & Analgesia. 126(5):1763-1768, May 2018.
12. Akhatov A., Renavikar A., Rashidov A., Nazarov F. “*Optimization of the number of databases in the Big Data processing*” Проблемы информатики, №

1(58) 2023, DOI: 10.24412/2073-0667-2023-1-33-47

13. Akhatov Akmal, Rashidov Akbar, Nazarov Fayzullo “*The Same Size Distribution of Data Based on Unsupervised Clustering Algorithms*” ICAILE2023: The 3rd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Logistics Engineering, March 11 - 12, 2023, Wuhan, China
14. A.R. Akhatov, A.E. Rashidov, F.M. Nazarov “*Increasing data reliability in big data systems*” // Scientific Journal of Samarkand State University 2021, №5, 106-14
15. Nazarov F., Akhatov A. & Rashidov A. “Consensus algorithms of blockchain technology of increasing the reliability of information” Fan va texnologiyalar taraqqiyoti, 2022/1/1